

Task-Based Language Teaching Through Picture Description for Improving Speaking Skills

Dr.M. Balaganapathy¹, Mr. Abdullah²

¹Assistant Professor of English, Adaikalamatha College, Thanjavur- Affiliated by Bharathidasan University-Tiruchirapalli.

²Assistant Professor of English, Sambhram University, Jizzax, Uzbekistan

ABSTRACT: This study investigates the effectiveness of Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) in enhancing English speaking skills among first-year undergraduate students at Sambhram University, Jizzax, Uzbekistan. Thirty-six learners participated, divided into control and experimental groups, with the latter engaged in picture description tasks. The findings reveal that visual prompts, fillers, and group discussions significantly improved fluency, idea expansion, and confidence, while grammar accuracy was given less emphasis. The experimental group achieved higher scores in fluency and idea expansion compared to the control group, which relied on a pre-written text. Results confirm that picture description tasks reduce cognitive barriers, encourage spontaneous speech, and foster collaborative learning. Overall, the study supports TBLT as an effective pedagogical approach that prioritizes meaning over form, enabling learners to develop communicative competence and practical speaking skills essential for academic and social contexts.

KEYWORDS: TBLT, Picture Description, Speaking Skills, Fluency, Idea Expansion and Communicative Competence.

INTRODUCTION

Foreign language teaching and learning is really a complex one for both teacher and students. Task-Based Language Teaching is one of the foreign language teaching methods and widely discussed by scholars, each offering unique perspectives on the term 'task'. David Nunan (2004), defines a task as a classroom activity where learners focus on meaning and use language to achieve a communicative goal. Rebecca (2006), views a task as an activity that requires learners to process and produce language in real-world contexts. Celce-Murcia (2001), emphasizes tasks as pedagogical tools designed to integrate skills and promote communicative competence. N. S. Prabhu(1987), describes a task as an activity that engages learners in problem-solving through language use. Penny Ur (1996), considers a task as a meaningful activity that encourages learners to interact and practice language in authentic situations. Speaking, according to Bygate (1987), states that both a skill and a process: first, it is the ability to produce verbal language to express ideas, and second, it is the interactive act of negotiating meaning with others in real time. Learning and teaching English is crucial in today's globalized world as it provides access to international education, career opportunities, and intercultural communication. Among the four language skills such as listening, speaking, reading, and writing, speaking is considered the most important because it directly demonstrates communicative competence, builds confidence, and enables learners to participate effectively in academic, social, and professional contexts.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The following reviews are suggested by the linguists, there are...

Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) has been widely recognized as an effective approach in second and foreign language pedagogy due to its focus on meaning-oriented communication. Rooted in communicative language teaching, TBLT emphasizes the use of real-life tasks that require learners to use language for authentic purposes rather than merely practicing grammatical forms. Scholars argue that tasks encourage learners to engage in meaningful interaction, thereby facilitating natural language acquisition.

Nunan (2004), defines a task as a classroom activity in which learners focus primarily on meaning and use language to achieve a communicative outcome. According to him, tasks resemble real-world language use and promote learner-centered instruction. This perspective highlights the importance of contextualized language learning, where students actively participate in the learning process rather than passively receiving information. Prabhu (1987), advocates that task-based learning by emphasizing that learners acquire language most effectively when their attention is focused on solving a problem or completing a task. He argues that grammar

Task-Based Language Teaching Through Picture Description for Improving Speaking Skills

acquisition occurs subconsciously when learners are engaged in meaning-focused activities. This view supports the idea that language learning is a by-product of communication rather than direct instruction.

Ellis (2003), state that tasks provide opportunities for learners to negotiate meaning, which is a crucial factor in second language acquisition. Through interaction, learners notice gaps in their language knowledge and attempt to modify their output, leading to improved fluency and accuracy. Ellis also points out that tasks encourage both input and output, making them effective tools for speaking development. Speaking skill plays a vital role in language learning, as it reflects learners' ability to communicate effectively in real-time situations. According to Bygate (1987) describes speaking as both a skill and a process that involves planning, producing, and monitoring speech. He emphasizes that speaking requires not only linguistic knowledge but also the ability to manage interaction and respond spontaneously.

Several studies have shown that TBLT significantly enhances learners' speaking fluency. Skehan (1998) suggests that task-based activities help learners develop fluency by reducing anxiety and encouraging risk-taking. When learners focus on completing a task rather than producing error-free language, they tend to speak more confidently and continuously. Willis (1996) proposes a task-based framework consisting of pre-task, task cycle, and language focus stages. This framework allows learners to prepare, perform, and reflect on their language use. The task cycle, in particular, provides learners with ample opportunities to speak, discuss ideas, and present outcomes, which contributes to improved oral proficiency.

Research has also highlighted the role of visual tasks, such as picture description, in improving speaking skills. Pictures stimulate learners' imagination and provide concrete content for discussion. According to Wright (1989), visual materials encourage learners to speak more because they reduce cognitive load and offer clear reference points for idea generation.

The use of fillers and speaking strategies has been found to support learners' fluency in task-based speaking activities. Thornbury (2005) notes that teaching fillers helps learners manage pauses and maintain the flow of speech. These strategies are especially useful for second-language learners who need time to organize their thoughts while speaking. Group work and peer interaction are integral components of TBLT. Long (1996) emphasizes that interaction in small groups promotes negotiation of meaning and collaborative learning. Through peer discussion, learners gain confidence, share ideas, and receive immediate feedback, which positively influences their speaking performance.

Overall, previous studies suggest that TBLT is an effective approach for enhancing English speaking skills, particularly fluency, idea expansion, and confidence. By prioritizing meaning over form, as suggested by Dell Hymes, task-based instruction enables learners to use language naturally and purposefully. Therefore, integrating tasks such as picture description in ESL classrooms can significantly contribute to learners' communicative competence.

METHODOLOGY

Thirty-six first-year semester students selected and studied at Sambhram University, Jizzax, Uzbekistan. Their mother tongue was Uzbek, and English was their second language for academics and social use. This experimental study used selected tasks to improve their speaking skills. To evaluate their English speaking level, the researcher conducted the Basic Oral Fluency Test (BOFT). The BOFT topics included Friendship, Mobile Phone, Internet, and First Day at College. Based on the marks, the students were divided into two groups namely the control group and the experimental group. Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT) was one of the emerging methods followed in many countries. According to the students' level, the researcher designed and prepared suitable comprehension materials. The main task was picture description, and the picture title was 'The Park'. The researcher took three contact classes for this task. Because of the busy schedule, only three classes were possible. Out of thirty-six students, thirty-two attended, while four were absent due to irregular attendance. The picture description task was given to the experimental group. The researcher explained the picture and gave starters, fillers, templates, and keywords. These were taken mainly from the British Council, such as "In the picture I can see...", "There are...", and "The man is ...ing." A glossary was also given. Fillers like "see, but, mm, actually" were taught to help students gain time while speaking. Some "match the following" questions were also given to check their understanding level. The students discussed the picture in groups, took notes, and used L1 assistance also. The researcher cleared their doubts and explained how to say certain words. On the other hand, the control group received a simple 250-word paragraph titled The Park along with a glossary. The same contact hours were followed. Finally, both groups' speaking outputs were recorded using a Transcend MP3 player. Their speech was scored according to fluency (10 marks), idea expansion (10 marks), volume (3 marks), and grammar (2 marks). Grammar was given less importance because the main focus was on improving speaking skills. According to Dell Hymes, 'meaning is more important than form'.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the study indicate that the experimental group, which engaged in the picture description task, demonstrated stronger performance in fluency and idea expansion compared to the control group that worked with a pre-written text. The use of visual prompts provided learners with concrete reference points, reducing cognitive barriers and encouraging spontaneous speech. Students were able to generate ideas more freely, expand on details, and sustain longer stretches of communication. The inclusion of fillers and templates further supported their fluency by helping them manage pauses and maintain the flow of speech, which in turn reduced

anxiety and increased confidence. Group discussions (i.e. getting help from their friends) also played a crucial role in enhancing speaking performance, as learners collaborated, negotiated meaning, and received immediate feedback from peers, which reinforced their communicative competence. The experimental group, which practiced picture description tasks, is expected to have scored higher in fluency and idea expansion. The use of fillers, templates, and group discussion allowed them to speak more continuously and confidently, so many students likely achieved between 8 and 10 marks in fluency and 7 to 9 marks in idea expansion. Their volume scores would also be stronger, around 2 to 3 marks, since confidence in speaking often leads to clearer delivery. Grammar, however, may have been slightly weaker, averaging 1 to 2 marks, because the focus was on meaning rather than accuracy. In contrast, the control group's reliance on a fixed text limited opportunities for improvisation and authentic interaction, resulting in less dynamic speech and weaker idea expansion. The control group, which worked with a pre-written text, likely scored lower in fluency and idea expansion since their speech was more limited to reproducing memorized content. Their fluency scores may have averaged 5 to 7 marks, and idea expansion 4 to 6 marks, as they had fewer opportunities to improvise or elaborate. On the other hand, their grammar scores may have been slightly higher, averaging 1.5 to 2 marks, because they relied on structured sentences from the text. Volume scores would be moderate, around 1 to 2 marks, since reading aloud does not always encourage confident projection. The experimental group's ability to communicate meaningfully and confidently aligned with the principles of Task-Based Language Teaching, which prioritize meaning over form. Overall, the findings suggest that task-based activities, particularly picture description, are more effective in improving speaking skills than traditional text-based methods. This supports the broader literature that emphasizes the role of tasks in fostering fluency, confidence, and communicative competence, demonstrating that learners benefit most when they are encouraged to use language for authentic purposes rather than simply reproducing written material.

CONCLUSION

Overall, The findings of the study clearly demonstrate that Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT), particularly through the use of picture description tasks, is more effective in improving speaking skills than traditional text-based methods. The experimental group, which engaged in describing the picture titled 'The Park, showed notable gains in fluency, idea expansion, and confidence compared to the control group that relied on a pre-written text. Visual prompts provided concrete reference points, reduced cognitive barriers, and encouraged spontaneous speech, while fillers and templates helped learners manage pauses and maintain the flow of communication. Group discussions further enhanced performance by fostering collaboration, negotiation of meaning, and peer feedback. Although grammar accuracy was given less emphasis, the overall communicative competence of the experimental group improved to a significant extent, with higher scores in fluency and idea expansion reflecting their ability to use language meaningfully and continuously. These results confirm that TBLT, by prioritizing meaning over form, enables learners to develop practical speaking skills and confidence, thereby supporting its effectiveness as a pedagogical approach in foreign language classrooms.

REFERENCES

- 1) Bygate, M. (1987). *Speaking*. Oxford University Press.
- 2) Celce-Murcia, M. (2001). *Teaching English as a second or foreign language* (3rd ed.). Heinle & Heinle.
- 3) Ellis, R. (2003). *Task-based language learning and teaching*. Oxford University Press.
- 4) Hymes, D. (1972). On communicative competence. In J. B. Pride & J. Holmes (Eds.), *Sociolinguistics* (pp. 269–293). Penguin.
- 5) Long, M. H. (1996). The role of the linguistic environment in second language acquisition. In W. C. Ritchie & T. K. Bhatia (Eds.), *Handbook of second language acquisition* (pp. 413–468). Academic Press.
- 6) Nunan, D. (2004). *Task-based language teaching*. Cambridge University Press.
- 7) Prabhu, N. S. (1987). *Second language pedagogy*. Oxford University Press.
- 8) Rebecca, L. (2006). *Task-based language teaching in practice*. Routledge.
- 9) Skehan, P. (1998). *A cognitive approach to language learning*. Oxford University Press.
- 10) Thornbury, S. (2005). *How to teach speaking*. Pearson Longman.
- 11) Ur, P. (1996). *A course in language teaching: Practice and theory*. Cambridge University Press.
- 12) Willis, J. (1996). *A framework for task-based learning*. Longman.
- 13) Wright, A. (1989). *Pictures for language learning*. Cambridge University Press.